

OPEN MICROWAVE HEATING OF POLYMER RESIN WITH DISPERSED CARBON NANOTUBES USING INTERDIGITAL ELECTRODE FILM

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ABSTRACT

Conventional microwave heating requires an expensive facility and its enclosed-type oven limits the size of curable products. This study proposes an open-type microwave heating of a polymer resin using microwaves produced by an interdigital electrode array film positioned between the composites and the mold. The proposed method has the advantages of reduced facility cost and applicability to large composite structures. The dispersion of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in the resin also enables the use of a relatively low applied voltage for the heating at high temperature. This is because the CNT-filled resin has a high dielectric loss tangent compare with pure resin. A formula for predicting the amount of heat generated was developed based on the impedance frequency characteristics corresponding to the CNT content of the resin. It was observed that the generated heat increased with the CNT content owing to the increased dielectric loss tangent of the resin due to the dispersed CNT. It was particularly observed that a significant temperature increase occurred at 0.08 wt% CNT content as a result of the electrical percolation phenomenon. Moreover, a microwave heating experiment produced an amount of heat comparable to that predicted by the developed formula, and a heating efficiency of about 70%. The use of an interdigital electrode array film to heat a large area produced an inhomogeneous temperature distribution when a voltage was applied to all the electrodes. However, the application of selective heating together with the MIEA produced a more uniform temperature distribution.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced plastics (FRPs) Fiber-reinforced plastics (FRPs) are generally composed of thermosetting resins such as epoxy and unsaturated polyester, and the manufacturing process therefore requires thermal curing. In conventional thermal curing using an oven or autoclave, massive thermal energy wastage of the process results in a negative heating efficiency. This has led to an increased interest in the use of microwave heating as an alternate curing method, owing to its speed, energy savings, and low cost [1, 2].

In microwave heating, a polymer resin in an electric field transduces electromagnetic energy into thermal energy through its dielectric loss. The phenomenon of internal heating directly raises the overall temperature of the resin [3]. Recent studies have investigated the dispersion of conductive fillers such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in liquid resins, with the aim of improving the heating value and cure cycle of microwave heating [4]. However, because conventional ovens and microwave heating oven, high costs are therefore involved in the development of equipment for heating large

structures. Furthermore, the depending on a power, a frequency of the equipment and dielectric loss tangent of the resin, the heating value may be low. These problems are importance to apply thermosetting resins for commercial products such as automobile.

To meet this need, we propose a cost-effective open microwave heating method that utilizes a thin electrode array film and CNT-filled resin. The film is set only between the composites and the mold, thereby enabling the curing of large structures. Moreover, since the dispersion of CNTs in the resin increases both the dielectric loss tangent and the generated heat, expensive high-voltage equipment are not required. Moreover, selective heating by controlling the electrode array is used to resolve the inhomogeneous temperature increase that results from the dielectric loss tangent of the mixture. An equivalent electric circuit model of the open microwave heating was constructed and used to predict the generated heat. Furthermore, the magnitudes of the generated heat for various CNT contents were experimentally determined and compared.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Multifunctional Interdigital Electrode Array

The resin was heated using a multifunctional interdigital electrode array (MIEA) developed by the authors [5-9]. Figure 1(a) shows the pattern of the copper electrodes and the wiring of the MIEA, which was fabricated by photolithography. The wiring was attached to the back of the polyimide film, which measured $200 \times 200 \times 0.013 \text{ mm}^3$ and was connected via a through-hole to the interdigital electrodes on the other side. The electrodes were aligned in a grid and the wires were divided into rows and columns. Wires 1, 2, ..., 5 were used to identify the longitudinal connections (the columns), and A, B, ..., E were used to identify the horizontal ones (the rows). Thus, there were 25 interdigital electrodes and 10 wires altogether, and the capacitive interdigital electrodes had input voltages of V+ and Ground. Figure 1(b) shows the cross-section of the interdigital electrode and the CNT-filled resin. Because the positive and negative electrodes were arranged alternately, each electrode generated an electric field in the resin in conjunction with its neighbor electrodes.

(b) Cross-sectional view of interdigital electrode with CNT-filled resin.
Figure 1. Multifunctional interdigital electrode array (MIEA) film for resin heating.

2.2 Microwave Heating of Resin

The temperature of a resin can be raised by microwave heating using a MIEA[10]. When a dielectric material such as a polyester resin is placed in the electric field, the dipoles of the resin align with the electric field, resulting in polarization. When the frequency of the electric field is much higher than the rotation of the dipole, movement is hindered, which results in frictional heating. The microwave heating value P of the resin is given by

$$P = VI \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \delta\right) \quad (1)$$

where V is the voltage applied to the dielectric resin, I is the current flowing through the resin, and δ is the loss angle of the resin.

For the dielectric material, $\delta \ll 1$, hence,

$$P = VI \sin \delta \approx VI \tan \delta \quad (2)$$

where $\tan \delta$ is the dielectric loss tangent, which was approximately 0.05 at about 1 kHz for the unsaturated polyester resin of this study.

The equivalent circuit of the MIEA was modeled by a resistor and capacitor in parallel. The electric current I that flows through the capacitor is

$$I = 2\pi f CV \quad (3)$$

where f is the frequency of the alternating voltage and C is the capacitance of the capacitor. By substituting Eq. (3) in Eq. (2), the heating value P can be rewritten using the applied voltage and the dielectric loss tangent of the resin as

$$P = 2\pi f CV^2 \tan \delta \quad (4)$$

It can be seen from the preceding equation that a higher voltage and dielectric loss tangent are required for a higher heating value at a given frequency. Pure polyester resin with a low $\tan \delta$ value of 0.05 requires a high voltage for sufficient heating value, which is the reason why conventional microwave heating requires expensive high-voltage equipment. However, the dispersion of CNTs in the resin is expected to increase the dielectric loss tangent [11, 12] and enable heating without the use of expensive facilities.

2.3 CNT-filled Resin

It is difficult to disperse CNTs in a polymer resin because the strong van der Waals force and high aspect ratio result in agglomeration [13-15]. Moreover, the agglomerates adversely affect the

mechanical and electrical properties of the products and necessitate an efficient dispersion process. Methods such as ultrasonication, calendaring, roll mill, and shear mixing have been applied [15, 16]. The ultrasonication and planetary mixing described below were used in this study because they are simple and efficient.

Immediately before the dispersion, the CNTs (VGCF-X, Showa Denko, length 3 μm , diameter 15 nm) were dried in an oven at 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 h, after which they were mixed with unsaturated polyester (PC-184-C, Sundhoma) in a planetary kneader machine (NBK-1, Nissei) at 1700 rpm for 3 min. Sample mixtures containing 0–1.0 wt% CNT were prepared and each was thereafter treated in an ultrasonic bath sonicator (US-2K, AS ONE) for 2 h, with further 3-min mixing in the kneader machine every 30 min. For comparison, a sample mixture of CB (Toka Black #4400, Tokai Carbon, particle diameter 38 nm) and the resin was also prepared by mixing in the kneader machine at 1700 rpm for 15 min.

2.4 Measurements of Impedance Frequency Characteristics

First, the equivalent circuit of the interdigital electrode and the CNT-filled resin was modeled to calculate the heating value of the resin. The impedance frequency characteristic of the resin was measured. Although the MIEA consisted of multiple interdigital electrodes, for convenience, the impedance measurement was performed using a single interdigital electrode. Figure 2 is a schematic of the experimental setup. The single interdigital electrode had a size of $20 \times 20 \times 0.085 \text{ mm}^3$ and 1 g of CNT-filled resin was poured into a frame placed on the interdigital electrode. The impedance Z and phase angle θ between 100 Hz and 5 MHz were measured using an LCR meter (Hioki 3535-50).

Figure 2. Impedance measurement setup of CNT-filled resin on interdigital electrode.

2.5 Microwave Heating Experiments

Microwave heating experiments were performed to compare the actual heat generated by the resin with that predicted by the equivalent circuit model. The experimental generated heat is represented by P_n and was measured by a thermograph. The alternating voltage of frequency 1 MHz was generated by a waveform generator (PXI 5421, National Instruments) and amplified through a high-frequency amplifier (T145-5527A, Thamway). The voltage was kept constant at 60 V_{pp} and monitored by an oscilloscope (TDS 2012B, Tektronix). The same CNT-filled resin samples and interdigital electrode used for measuring the impedance frequency characteristics were used for this experiment. After 20 s of microwave heating, the temperature increase ΔT was measured using a thermograph (CPA-0170, Chino). The different CNT-filled resin samples differed in appearance and temperature change. The amount of heat generated P_n was calculated from the measured temperatures using the following:

$$dP_n = \frac{c\Delta T}{t} dm \quad (5)$$

$$P_n = \frac{c}{t} \int_V \Delta T dm$$

where c is the specific heat of the pure resin, which was used because the low CNT content had no significant effect on it [17].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Equivalent Model of Interdigital Electrode with CNT-filled resin

Figures 3(a) and (b) respectively show the resistance R and reactance X of each sample of the resin at 1 MHz. R and X were calculated using the following:

$$R = |Z| \cos \theta \quad (6)$$

$$X = |Z| \sin \theta$$

In addition, the dielectric loss tangent was calculated using

$$\tan \delta = |R / X| \quad (7)$$

Figure 3(c) shows the dielectric loss tangent for each sample of the resin.

The impedance Z describes a variety of radial semicircles on the complex plane. The behavior of the frequency approached that of the equivalent circuit model. The capacitance C_p was calculated from the change in the reactance X between two frequencies, because it could not be read from the semicircle. The impedance Z is expressed as a function of the angular frequency:

$$Z = R + jX$$

$$= \left\{ \frac{R_p}{(\omega C_p R_p)^2 + 1} + R_s \right\} + j \left\{ \frac{-\omega C_p R_p^2}{(\omega C_p R_p)^2 + 1} \right\} \quad (8)$$

where R_p and C_p are assumed to be constant regardless of the angular frequency. From Eq. (8), C_p can be expressed as

$$C_p = \frac{\left(\frac{\omega_2}{X_2} - \frac{\omega_1}{X_1} \right)}{\omega_1^2 - \omega_2^2} \quad (9)$$

where ω_1 and ω_2 are the angular frequencies between two different frequencies, and X_1 and X_2 are the reactances between the angular frequencies.

In Figures 3(a)–(c), the dielectric loss tangent of the resin gradually increases with the CNT content between 0 and 0.06 wt% because R increases and $|X|$ decreases. Beyond 0.08 wt%, R begins to decrease and $|X|$ decreases much faster. This shows that the greater increase in the dielectric loss tangent is due to the dispersed CNTs. The changes in the electrical properties are suspected to be specifically related to the electrical percolation of the dispersed CNTs. Moreover, the rapid dielectric loss tangent that occurs for a CNT content of 0.08 wt% approximately corresponds to the percolation threshold of the CNT-filled resin [11, 16, 18, 19].

Figure 3. Electrical characteristics of interdigital electrode with CNT-filled resin for 1 MHz.

3.2 Prediction of Power Consumption Based on Equivalent Circuit

The heating results from the serial resistance R_s and parallel resistance R_p in the equivalent circuit model and can therefore be considered as the power consumption of the resistive components. It is possible to calculate the power consumption at a given frequency from the values obtained from the LCR meter. This power consumption, denoted by P_L , is given by Joule's law as

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_L &= I^2 R \\
 &= \left(\frac{V}{\sqrt{R^2 + X^2}} \right)^2 R
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

However, P_L can only be used to predict the power consumption at a specific frequency of the LCR meter. Considering the equivalent circuit model, the power consumption P_m can be expressed as a function of the angular frequency:

$$P_m = \frac{V^2}{\left\{ \frac{R_p}{(\omega C_p R_p)^2} + R_s \right\}^2 + \left\{ \frac{-\omega C_p R_p^2}{(\omega C_p R_p)^2 + 1} \right\}^2} R \tag{11}$$

From the above, the resistance R and reactance X can be calculated from R_s , R_p , and C_p . It is thus possible to predict the consumed power at an arbitrary angular frequency using the equivalent circuit model.

3.3 Generated heat of CNT-filled resin

Figure 4 compares the model power consumption P_m obtained using Eq. (11) and the amount of heat generated P_n obtained using Eq. (5). In addition, the power consumption P_L based on the LCR meter reading at 1 MHz is calculated using Eq. (10). It can be seen from Figure 4 that P_n is less than 0.1 W for 0–0.06 wt% CNT content, which is because the temperature of the resin hardly increased. For 0.08 wt% CNT content, there is a noticeable temperature increase, which continues with increasing CNT content. At 1.0 wt%, the temperature exceeds 30°C and P_n is above 1.8 W. The applicability of the three elements of the equivalent circuit model is also confirmed by the agreement between the values of P_m and P_L . Moreover, the patterns of the variation of P_m and P_n with the CNT content are similar, although P_m is always higher.

The increase in P_m at 0.08 wt% CNT content is mainly due to the reduction in $|X|$ as can be seen in Figure 3(b). Above 0.1 wt% CNT content, P_m further increases as R reduces. In other words, the microwave heating improves as a result of the increased conductivity and dielectric loss tangent that occur in the resin with increasing CNT content.

We also examined the efficiency of the microwave heating using P_m and P_n . The approximate function ($R^2 = 0.962$) has a gradient of 0.70, which makes the efficiency approximately 70%. This efficiency is higher than that of a conventional oven, which is 20–50%.

Figure 4. Electric power P : Power consumptions P_m and P_L , and generated heat P_n of interdigital electrode with CNT-filled resin for applied voltage of 60 V_{pp}, 1 MHz.

4. CONCLUSION

We examined the open microwave heating characteristics of a CNT-filled resin for use in low-cost curing of large composite structures. A formula for predicting the amount of heat generated was developed based on the impedance frequency characteristics corresponding to the CNT content of the resin. It was observed that the generated heat increased with the CNT content owing to the increased dielectric loss tangent of the resin due to the dispersed CNT. It was particularly observed that a significant temperature increase occurred at 0.08 wt% CNT content as a result of the electrical percolation phenomenon. Moreover, a microwave heating experiment produced an amount of heat comparable to that predicted by the developed formula, and a heating efficiency of about 70%. The use of a MIEA to heat a large area produced an inhomogeneous temperature distribution when a voltage was applied to all the electrodes. However, the application of selective heating together with the MIEA produced a more uniform temperature distribution.

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